

Development and Validation Web 2.0 Extensive Listening Materials using the ICE Framework for English for Specific Purposes Students

Surti Milarisa

English Education Department, Universitas Negeri Semarang, Central Java, Indonesia

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0942-7743>

***Rudi Hartono**

*Corresponding Author: rudi.hartono@students.unnes.ac.id

English Education Department, Universitas Negeri Semarang, Central Java, Indonesia

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9331-8744>

Abdurrachman Faridi

English Education Department, Universitas Negeri Semarang, Central Java, Indonesia

<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2582-4555>

Yuliati Yuliati

English Education Department, Universitas Negeri Semarang, Central Java, Indonesia

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5991-290X>

Abstract

Background: Extensive Listening (EL) involves using authentic audio and video materials to improve language skills through enjoyable, out-of-class exposure. In ESP contexts, this approach is more complex due to the need for specific content knowledge. However, suitable and engaging Web 2.0 EL materials that use the ICE (interesting, comprehensible, and enjoyable) framework for English for Specific Purposes (ESP) learners remain limited.

Objective: This study aimed to develop and validate Web 2.0 EL materials based on the ICE framework and examine students' perceptions of the validated materials.

Methodology: The study implemented the ADDIE model. A needs analysis questionnaire was distributed to 255 students and 42 ESP lecturers across five provinces. In the development phase,

three experts reviewed the web model, EL, and text structure. The Mann-Whitney U test measured differences in perceptions, while NVivo was used to code interviews.

Results: Web 2.0 EL materials using the ICE Framework for ESP students have been developed and validated. The need analysis results showed that 75.6% of students strongly agreed that interesting listening materials are important. For fun activities, 49.5% strongly agreed that EL would be fun. The findings showed no significant difference between students' and lecturers' perceptions of developing and validating Web 2.0 EL materials using the ICE framework, but a significant difference regarding the statement about using web-based learning materials as a solution.

Conclusion: The limited research focus on EL in ESP highlights the need for more targeted learning resources. The development of Web 2.0 ICE-based materials offers a promising solution for promoting independent and engaging listening practice tailored to specific learner needs.

Key Recommendation: Future ESP listening instruction should incorporate Web 2.0 materials designed with the ICE (*Interesting, Comprehensible, and Enjoyable*) framework to support autonomous, engaging, and relevant learning.

Keywords: ICE framework, extensive listening, ESP students, Web 2.0

Introduction

Extensive Listening (EL) can be defined as a language learning approach that involves listening to a wide variety of authentic learning materials such as radio broadcasts, podcasts, web, TV programs, videos, lectures, audiobooks, and the Internet (Ivone & Renandya, 2019). When learners engage in extensive listening, they typically listen to longer stretches of audio or video materials without feeling anxious about comprehension checks and memory tests, as they receive a substantial amount of meaningful input and participate in listening activities for pleasure outside the classroom. This approach provides a large quantity of meaningful input, such as facial expression, language in context, intonation, and gestures, to foster students' overall listening comprehension and other language skills without necessarily relying on a single word or phrase (Mayora, 2017; Renandya & Jacobs, 2016).

In the context of English as a foreign or second language learning (EFL/ESL), learners use the above wide variety of English authentic learning materials to enhance their language performance and cultural awareness also, the authentic materials have the principle to help language learners expand their knowledge by providing them with opportunities to comprehend and use English outside of the classroom (Arifani et al., 2024), but in the English for Specific Purposes (ESP) field, EL becomes more complex as it involves not only the English language but also specific content knowledge and specific English needs (Vuković-Stamatović, 2022). The complexity of ESP involves several issues. First, it deals with teacher quality. Most teachers who teach ESP have graduated from the English Education department, but they do not have ESP background knowledge (Lichterfeld, 2024; Meristo & López, 2020). Second, ESP course materials are commonly designed for general English with little attention to specific content knowledge curricula (Chan, 2024). Similarly, numerous studies on classroom teaching listening for ESP put a bigger emphasis on improving teaching strategy to improve learners' language development rather than analysing the relevance between listening materials and their learners' specific content knowledge and English learning needs (Smith et al., 2022). In addition, García and Gómez (2023)

investigate ten Spain ESP lecturers related to the courses they teach. Meanwhile, EL materials for the purpose of learning for enjoyment outside the classroom as a meaningful input for ESP are still unavailable. Students often rely heavily on authentic listening materials (such as videos, audiobooks, radio broadcasts, and TV programs), which are unsuitable for their specific learning and target needs (Simpson, 2024). They cannot provide meaningful and real-life experiences for the ESP students to support their specific English skills in their field.

Literature Review

Interesting Comprehensible Enjoyable (ICE) principles in developing Extensive Listening Web 2.0 for ESP

Interesting, Comprehensible, and Enjoyable (ICE) principles consist of three elements: interesting, comprehensible, and enjoyable. The first element is an *interesting* principle. In the context of ESP, this principle highlights the importance of aligning listening materials with the specific needs of content knowledge, industry-specific vocabulary, concepts, and English for certain academic or professional purposes. The second element is a *comprehensible* principle. This principle refers to the comprehensibility of the EL materials that reflect students' language proficiency levels. This idea aligns with Krashen's Input Hypothesis, which emphasises the need for input slightly above the learners' current level ($i+1$) to promote effective language learning (Krashen & Mason, 2020). The third element is an *enjoyable principle*, which emphasizes leveraging Web 2.0 tools to create a pleasurable listening experience tailored to professional or academic interests. Web 2.0 platforms such as YouTube, podcasts, and interactive web applications offer a diverse range of authentic materials that can make learning more enjoyable. By integrating Web 2.0 tools into ESP listening activities, educators can provide access to current and relevant materials, making the learning experience more engaging, enjoyable, pertinent and stimulating, leading to improved language acquisition and professional knowledge.

EL in ESP context and related previous studies in EL

Extensive Listening (EL) refers to a language learning approach that encourages language learners to be exposed to and engaged in a large amount of comprehensible and enjoyable materials presented in the target language over extended periods of time to develop their overall comprehension skills (Aldukhayel, 2019). Within the context of English for Specific Purposes (ESP), EL is tailored to the specific language needs of learners within their professional or academic domains. It focuses on developing listening skills relevant to their field, such as listening to lectures, presentations, interviews, or discussions related to their area of expertise. The learning activities of EL in ESP often involve listening to a wide range of highly specialised materials directly related to the learners' professional or academic interests.

The emergence of EL is stimulated by the effectiveness of the extensive reading (ER) approach that facilitates learning through frequent reading (Renandya & Jacobs, 2016). Consequently, the effectiveness of listening skills could be best achieved through frequent listening or EL; & Renandya, 2019). Implementing EL in L2 teaching, especially in the ESP context, is a relatively new approach, and its theoretical framework is undeveloped, so not many language teachers have the knowledge to carry it out. Although some scholars (Chang & Millett, 2014) have emphasized

the need for implementing EL to enhance L2 learners' listening skills, few studies can be identified in the currently available literature.

In the previous research, Simpson (2024) argued that ESP materials for accounting have been pedagogical considerations. The evaluation of the materials includes the level of students' listening ability in relation to the level of the material provided, appropriateness for the target learners' needs, alignment with learning objectives, suitability of the teaching methodology, naturalness and contextualization of language models, and support for learner autonomy. The checklist includes an evaluation of transactional and phatic communication, realistic meeting chair and participant language, politeness strategies, formality, meeting structure, and sensitivity to cultural differences. The checklists provide key findings on the topic of business meetings. With some adaptation work on the checklists for the local context, they can serve as a supportive framework for in-depth analysis to identify gaps in learner needs and materials (Chan, 2024).

Ivone and Renandya (2019) proposed three reasons why EL has not been widely used in the EL context. First, they claimed that many researchers still do not understand the concept of EL well, and this is compounded by the lack of publications related to EL in EFL/ESL scholarly journals, especially in the field of ESP (Chang & Millett, 2016). Second, the difficulty level of the material in EL, combined with limited EL resources and students' learning preferences, presents obstacles to implementing EL. Therefore, students often become discouraged and dislike EL courses (Renandya & Day, 2020; Turan-Öztürk & Tekin, 2020). Third, the lack of availability of EL material is enjoyable, interesting, and comprehensible. Consequently, from the three reasons above, the need for EL material extends not only to EFL but also to ESP, and because EL is Interesting, Comprehensible, and Enjoyable (ICE), this research aims to develop EL material for ESP using these three frameworks.

The study was conducted in two stages. The first stage was completed with developed and validated Web 2.0 EL materials using the ICE framework for ESP students, and the second stage was analyzing the perception of the developed product. Based on the proposed research gap, the research questions are formulated into:

- 1) How can Web 2.0 Extensive Listening materials using the ICE framework for ESP students be developed and validated?
2. What is the perception of the students and lecturers on the developed and validated Web 2.0 Extensive Listening materials using the ICE framework for ESP students?

Based on the research questions above, this study aims to develop and validate extensive Web 2.0-based listening materials based on the *Interesting, Comprehensible, and Enjoyable* (ICE) framework, specifically tailored to the learning needs of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) students in higher education. Furthermore, this study also aims to investigate students' and lecturers' perceptions regarding the pedagogical effectiveness, relevance, and applicability of the developed materials, thereby providing empirical evidence supporting their integration into ESP listening instruction.

Meanwhile, the main contribution of this study is the development and validation of Web 2.0-based extensive listening materials using the *Interesting, Comprehensible, and Enjoyable* (ICE)

framework, specifically designed to meet the needs of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) students. This innovation integrates ICE principles to enhance engagement, comprehension, and enjoyment, leverages Web 2.0 technology for accessibility and interactivity, and is grounded in a needs analysis of students and lecturers, ensuring relevance and effectiveness for higher education contexts.

Methodology

Research Design

The present study aimed to develop and validate Web 2.0 EL materials using the ICE framework and explore students' perceptions regarding the validated Web 2.0 EL materials using the ICE framework.

Research Procedures

Based on the research design above, which uses the R&D research procedure as the ADDIE Model. This research was carried out by following the research procedures in the subsequent steps:

Figure 1 Research Procedures

1. Identifying the students' and the lecturers' need analysis

Before conducting the needs analysis, the researcher conducted a literature review to dig into some important information related to the needs of the students. This needs analysis applied a descriptive qualitative method to analyze data. The questionnaire was used to collect data from students of accounting study programs from nine universities across five provinces in Indonesia.

2. The second phase is Design

This phase consisted of the process of creating the prototype of the ICE framework. This stage also described the draft of four components of the Interesting, Comprehensible, and Enjoyable EL(henceforth ICE EL) framework.

Interesting

The term interesting in this model permits students to:

- a) To have interesting material based on the student's level of understanding.
- b) To build their interest in listening through web-based technological support.

Comprehensible

- a) To stay calm and focused—stress interferes with comprehensible
- b) To continuously practice to improve your comprehensive
- c) To distinguish among different response types—including judgments, empathy, opinions, and questions.
- d) To replay to ensure that you have understood completely
- e) To listen for emotional messages as well as words

Enjoyable

- a) To do not multi-task when listening—focus entirely on the speaker and enjoy
- b) To eliminate distractions
- c) To position themselves where it is easy to hear
- d) To postpone listening if you cannot concentrate
- e) Having the joyful material will improve your listening comprehension.

3. The third phase was to develop a preliminary of the product

After completing the prototype, the focus moved to refining and validating the EL framework. This process involved three validation stages: evaluating the website's functionality, ensuring the EL model aligned with ELT goals, and reviewing the accuracy of material structure and translation. Experts in grammar, translation, and design assessed the content to ensure quality and coherence.

4. The fourth phase was the Implementation

This phase focused on model testing to prove the utility of the ICE EL framework. A practical test will be executed by giving accounting study program students a questionnaire. A questionnaire will be provided to explore their perceptions after using this model.

5. The fifth phase was the evaluation

The next phase was evaluation, which focused on assessing and reviewing the results from the expert validation process. Based on the feedback received, improvements are made to refine and enhance the ICE EL framework to become a more validated and reliable model.

Participant and Setting

The analysis phase aims to probe students' need for Web 2.0 EL Materials using the ICE Framework. The study sample for this phase consisted of 255 undergraduate students enrolled in accounting programs from nine universities across five provinces. Participants were selected using convenience sampling. Both students and 42 lecturers of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) from the same universities as students filled out an online questionnaire.

Instruments

Development of ICE EL model questionnaires

To answer the research questions, two ICE-based questionnaires were distributed to students and lecturers: a needs analysis and a perception survey, each with 15 Likert-scale items covering interest, comprehension, and enjoyment. Three experts validated the content, and a pilot test with 59 students confirmed the strong reliability of the instrument (Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.85$). The ICE model, including web design and video texts, was also reviewed and validated by experts.

Interview

After collecting the questionnaires, online interviews were conducted with students and lecturers to gain deeper insights. Five open-ended questions explored their satisfaction, understanding, and opinions about the Web 2.0 EL materials using the ICE framework. Semi-structured interviews with five lecturers included similar questions, focusing on teaching experiences, challenges, and suggestions for improvement.

Data Collection and Analysis

The study followed the ADDIE model, beginning with an analysis phase through a needs assessment involving 255 students and 42 ESP lecturers from five provinces. Expert-validated questionnaires based on the ICE framework were used. In the development phase, three experts reviewed the web model, listening content, and text structure. During implementation, student and lecturer perceptions were examined using statistical analysis (Mann-Whitney U test) and qualitative interviews. NVivo supported data coding, word frequency, and pattern analysis for comparing responses.

Findings

How can Web 2.0 EL materials using the ICE framework for ESP students be developed and validated?

1. Needs Analysis of the Developed ICE Framework

a. Students' Needs Analysis

The ICE-based questionnaire was tested for validity and reliability to analyze student needs for developing Web 2.0-based EL material with the ICE framework. It was answered by 255 students from 9 campuses and 5 provinces in Indonesia to identify the target and learning needs in listening materials. A total of 75.6% of students strongly agreed that interesting materials for listening learning are important. Data showed 57.5% felt varied materials could help with listening difficulties, while only 3% disagreed. About 66% strongly agreed on

comprehensible materials, and 63% preferred an ICE framework. For enjoyable activities, 49.5% strongly agreed that EL would be fun. Researchers found the mean to be 51.4, the standard deviation is 8.377, and the median is 53.00.

b. Lecturers' Need Analysis

This section presents the results of a needs analysis questionnaire administered to 42 ESP lecturers regarding the ICE EL framework. This analysis identifies specific needs and gaps in current listening practices, as perceived by the lecturers, to determine the need and relevance of developing an ICE EL framework. Based on a questionnaire, 57.1% of lecturers need an interesting Web 2.0 learning model for teaching listening classes, highlighting the need for an ICE framework. Additionally, 66.7% prefer an interesting, comprehensible, and enjoyable teaching model, with only 2.4% against it. Furthermore, 61.9% seek comprehensible listening materials from various sources, while 66.7% find it hard to find authentic materials. To address these issues, a new learning model must be developed. Also, 57.1% want access to a visually appealing web model that promotes enjoyment in learning, supported by 52—4%.

2. Design of ICE EL Framework

Following the analysis phase, the design phase focused on developing learning materials, including syllabi, lesson plans, self-assessments, videos, and a web-based platform. The Web 2.0 EL materials using the ICE framework were designed to be flexible and adaptable through the website <https://ice-el.id/>. Learning units were structured using the Hurrier Listening Framework to support extensive listening and foster learner autonomy. Course videos were enhanced using Leonardo AI, and self-assessments were included to measure student progress over a one-semester program.

3. Develop Phase of ICE EL Framework

In the development phase, researchers finalized the teaching materials and validated the video content based on the ICE EL Web 2.0 framework. Materials were uploaded as videos aligned with course themes, and the website featured lesson plans, teaching procedures, and SEFL scoring. Students kept progress diaries, while lecturers provided guidance. Lecture videos were also included to support flexible learning for students unable to attend in person.

Expert validation covered three areas: the web platform, the EL framework, and the translated script, syllabus, and lesson plans. The results were positive, with the web component rated 3.3, design 3.75, and functionality and security scoring 4. The EL framework scored 3.4 for interest and comprehension, and 3 for enjoyment. Minor revisions were suggested for the self-assessment, while the translated material received a strong average score of 3.7, reflecting clarity and structure.

Figure 2. Web 2.0 EL Materials using ICE Framework

What is the perception of the students and lecturers on the developed and validated Web 2.0 EL materials using the ICE framework for ESP students?

4. Implementation

In this phase, materials have been created and used. The videos cover banking topics like asking about tellers, setting up accounts, withdrawing money, transferring funds, reporting a stuck ATM card, checking bank hours, and inquiring about ATMs. These videos were uploaded online and taught using the ICE EL framework. Results from the Mann-Whitney U test indicated no significant difference in perceptions of both groups on items 1-4, but a significant difference was found on item 5 regarding web-based learning solutions. (see table 1)

Items	Participants	N	M	SD	Mann Whitney U Test	pvalue
The ELmodel web 2.0 based ...	Lecturer	42	3.57	.547	4689.5	0.091
	Student	256	3.64	0.710		
ICE EL model WEB 2.0 based ...	Lecturer	42	3.57	0.501	5283	0.871
	Student	256	3.51	0.741		
The learning materials ...	Lecturer	42	3.45	0.670	4688	0.149
	Student	256	3.56	0.717		
The selection of color patterns ...	Lecturer	42	3.52	0.552	5272	0.853
	Student	256	3.48	0.736		
Material packaged with ...	Lecturer	42	3.67	0.477	4620	0.048
	Student	256	3.73	0.676		

Table 1. “Interesting Aspect” Students’ and lecturers’ perception

The perspective of the "comprehensible" aspect from the Mann-Whitney U test calculation shows that the perception of both groups of participants that dominantly there is no significant difference between students and lecturers' perspectives, both groups agree in the teaching/learning materials are comprehensible, this teaching material contains comprehensible vocabulary, this ELmodel improves their listening material and increases their teaching/learning ELreferences. Exceptions to materials are easy to learn/teach; there is a significant difference between students' and lecturer's perceptions, and the students agree with this statement. (see table 2).

Items	Participants	N	M	SD	Mann Whitney U Test	pvalue
The teaching/learning materials ...	Teacher	42	3.52	0.505	4741	0.143
	Student	256	3.57	0.716		
This teaching material contains ...	Teacher	42	3.48	0.594	4884	0.267
	Student	256	3.54	0.685		
This ELmodel improves ...	Teacher	42	3.67	0.477	2597	0.000
	Student	256	2.79	0.977		
Increasing my teaching...	Teacher	42	3.62	0.492	4876	0.269
	Student	256	3.46	0.685		
The materials are easy ...	Teacher	42	3.67	0.477	2947	0.000
	Student	256	2.96	0.898		

All participants agreed that the ICE EL framework met all enjoyable perspective categories. Teaching/learning English in an autonomous environment enjoyable. Keeping logs and journals about listening progress was helpful. There were a few unfamiliar words, and difficulties in listening to the materials did not occur. The engaging materials were accessible. Table 9 displays perceptions of the ICE framework's enjoyable aspects. Mann-Whitney U-test results show no significant differences between teachers' and students' perceptions.

Teachers' and learners' perspectives on their satisfaction with Web 2.0 ELMaterials using ICE

I believe it does. The ICE framework, because it focuses on materials that everyone can understand and relate to (including popular culture), offers clear direction when teachers are choosing the types of resources students will be listening to, as content is crucial when it comes to them being able to listen well. [L7]

Definitely yes, this application is rarely found in listening learning. Listening material that is only in the form of voice recordings, difficult, and too many tests is very different from ICE extensive listening. [L8]

I think so; this model has easier language construction, which helps students better understand, as proposed by the ICE EL teaching framework, besides easy access. [L11]

Yes, because it uses a display that is attractive, easy to understand, and fun. [S17]

Because I prefer to learn with interesting models, including Leonardo, I think this kind of learning model is perfect for me. [S22]

Yes, The ICE EL framework is quite satisfactory because it balances intensive listening for deep understanding and ELto expand skills. [S25]

Most students responded positively to their satisfaction with using the ICE framework. However, a student [S1] responded that she did not understand some of the problematic vocabulary in the video text due to her limited vocabulary.

Teachers' and learners' perspectives of their difficulty on Web 2.0 EL Materials using ICE Framework experience.

One of the main challenges in implementing the ICE Web 2.0 EL materials was helping students engage with unfamiliar, finance-specific vocabulary. To address this, lecturers used pre-listening strategies such as vocabulary previews and contextual discussions, which improved students' comprehension and readiness. While some students found formal financial terms difficult, they responded positively by practising more and learning from their mistakes. Students and lecturers highlighted different aspects of the ICE materials that caught their attention. Students appreciated the visual images, graphs, and engaging video design, particularly those created using the Leonardo AI tool. Lecturers valued the platform's complete teaching features, including lesson plans, self-assessments, and easy navigation. NVivo word cloud analysis confirmed that "listening" and "web" were the most frequently mentioned terms, emphasising the core focus of the model. Keywords such as "interesting," "enjoyable," "autonomous," and "comprehensible" reflect the principles of the ICE framework, while "accounting" and "specific" confirm the ESP context. Terms like "Leonardo" and "AI" highlight the digital tools used to enhance learning materials.

5. Evaluation

In the final phase, the ICE framework platform was evaluated based on the perceptions of both students and lecturers. This evaluation aimed to identify challenges and gather suggestions for improvement. Participants completed self-assessments involving authentic tasks, which revealed usability issues that had previously been overlooked. After analysing the questionnaire responses, researchers reviewed the feedback, proposed solutions, and formulated recommendations for enhancing the model.

Discussion

Although second language listening has gained research interest in the past decade, areas like fluency and extensive listening (EL) remain underexplored (Permadi et al., 2017; Shehzad et al., 2021). This study developed and validated Web 2.0-based ICE EL materials, exploring students' and lecturers' perceptions. Questionnaire results revealed no significant difference between the two groups in most areas, except for the belief that web-based materials provide a useful solution, where students showed stronger agreement. Both groups agreed that the materials were easy to understand, included accessible vocabulary, and enriched listening resources. However, students rated the materials as easier to learn than lecturers did.

The Mann-Whitney U test also found no significant difference in how enjoyable the materials were perceived, aligning with the idea that EL involves listening for pleasure through engaging media like movies, music, and online content. For EL to be effective, materials must be interesting,

understandable, diverse, and level-appropriate. Interviews revealed students' satisfaction with the ICE model and highlighted challenges with domain-specific vocabulary, which lecturers addressed through pre-teaching strategies and contextual support. Both students and lecturers appreciated the user-friendly web features, while students especially noted the visual appeal of materials enhanced by the Leonardo app. Overall, the study supports using technology and the internet as effective tools for EL, as also noted in recent research (Gonulal, 2022; Pamuji & Setyarini, 2020)

Conclusion

This study has developed and validated Web 2.0 EL Materials using ICE Framework with five phases: Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation. In the analysis phase, the researchers have proven that lecturers and students responded highly to the interesting, comprehensible, and enjoyable aspects. Meanwhile, the results of student and lecturer interviews showed a challenge, as most students had difficulty understanding the specific financial vocabulary used in EL activities. To overcome this challenge, the lecturer implemented a strategy of pre-teaching key terms and providing contextualization, increasing students' readiness to understand the material. Dominantly, lecturers and students gave positive answers to things that caught their attention in the Web 2.0 EL Materials using the ICE Framework, such as being helped by the menu on the web. In contrast, students were mostly impressed with the images produced by the Leonardo application included in the video material. In the implementation phase, it has been validated by 3 experts in the field of web, EL models, and translation aspects. Some inputs in the form of menu attachments originally in PDF form have been changed to HTML. Other minor inputs have also been revised for a more proven ICE framework.

The scarcity of EL materials has become an issue in learning listening. The lack of research attention on EL is the reason for the limited availability of the EL framework. Developing the Web 2.0 EL Materials using the ICE Framework with various menu features for autonomous learning is a breakthrough and solution in learning listening that sometimes does not get much attention.

References

- Aldukhayel. (2019). Vlogs in L2 listening: EFL learners' and teachers' perceptions. *Computer-Assisted Language Learning*. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 1–20.
- Arifani, Y., Rafiek, M., Lambung Mangkurat, U., Kalimantan, B., Yaoping LIU, I., McNeill, A., & Biyanto, B. (2024). Assessing Online TBLT Practices using RAIS Frameworks: In-service EFL Teachers' and Students' Perspectives. In *Computer Assisted Language Learning Electronic Journal (CALL-EJ)* (Vol. 25, Issue 1).
- Chan, C. S. C. (2024). Strengthening the interface between research and pedagogy in business English and beyond. *English for Specific Purposes*, 74, 23–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2008.12.001>
- Chang, A. C. S., & Millett, S. (2016). Developing L2 Listening Fluency through Extended Listening-focused Activities in an Extensive Listening Programme. *RELC Journal*, 47(3), 349–362. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0033688216631175>
- García, C., & Gómez, I. (2023). Science dissemination videos as multimodal supporting resources for ESP teaching in higher education. *English for Specific Purposes*, 70, 164–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2022.12.005>

- Gonulal, T. (2022). Improving Listening Skills with Extensive Listening Using Podcasts and Vodcasts. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 7(1), 311–320. <https://doi.org/10.33200/ijcer.685196>
- Ivone, F. M., & Renandya, W. A. (2019). Extensive listening and viewing in ELT. *Teflin Journal*, 30(2), 237–256. <https://doi.org/10.15639/teflinjournal.v30i2/237-256>
- Krashen, S. , & Mason, B. (2020). The optimal input hypothesis: Not all comprehensible input is of equal value. *CATESOL Newsletter*, 5(5), 1–2. <http://beniko-mason.net/content/articles/2019-GSSR-before-SSR.pdf>
- Lichterfeld, K. (2024). A practitioner’s commentary on C. Chan (2019): Long-term workplace communication needs of business professionals. *English for Specific Purposes*, 74, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2019.07.003>
- Mayora, C. A. (2017). Extensive Listening in a Colombian University: Process, Product, and Perceptions. *HOW*, 24(1), 101–121. <https://doi.org/10.19183/how.24.1.311>
- Meristo, M., & López Arias, F. J. (2020). Challenges in teaching english for specific purposes in estonian universities. *Journal of Teaching English for Specific and Academic Purposes*, 8(3), 249–263. <https://doi.org/10.22190/JTESAP2003249M>
- Pamuji, K. D., & Setyarini, S. (2020). Technology for Extensive Listening Practice: EFL Teachers’ Preferences and Views. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, 77–81. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3404709.3404712>
- Permadi, M. B., Sholihah, F. A., & Umamah, A. (2017). Extensive listening: Listen to the EFL teacher’s voices. *International Seminar on Language, Education, and Culture*, 195–202.
- Renandya, W. A., & Day, R. (2020). *The primacy of extensive reading and listening: Putting theory into practice*. In D. S. Anshori, P. Purnawarman, W. Gunawan, & Y. Wirza (Eds.), *Language, education, and policy for the changing society: Contemporary research and practices (Festschrift for Professor Fuad Abdul Hamied)*. Bandung, Indonesia: UPI Press.
- Renandya, W. A., & Jacobs, G. M. (2016). Extensive Reading and Listening in the L2 Classroom. In *English Language Education* (Vol. 5, pp. 97–110). Springer Science and Business Media B.V. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-38834-2_8
- Shehzad, M. W., Albeshar, K. B., Sarfraz, S., & Razzaq, S. (2021). Listening boredom, listening boredom coping strategies, and listening performance: Exploring the possible relationships in saudi EFL context. *Journal of Language and Education*, 7(3), 136–150. <https://doi.org/10.17323/JLE.2021.12875>
- Simpson, A. (2024). A practitioner’s commentary on C. Chan (2009): “Forging a link between research and pedagogy: A holistic framework for evaluating business English materials.” *English for Specific Purposes*, 74(2), 48–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2008.12.001>
- Smith, G. F., Jung, H., & Zenker, F. (2022). From task-based needs analysis to curriculum evaluation: Putting methodological innovations to the test in an English for academic purposes program. *English for Specific Purposes*, 66, 80–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2022.01.001>
- Turan Öztürk, D., & Tekin, S. (2020). Encouraging extensive listening in language learning. *Language Teaching Research Quarterly*, 14, 80-93.
- Vuković-Stamatović, M. (2022). Suitability of science & technology documentaries for EAP and EST listening. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2022.101137>